

DESIGN OF AUTOMATED TROLLEY TO DELIVER ESSENTIALS TO ISOLATED PATIENT

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Abstract

The current pandemic of COVID-19 is very difficult for medical authorities to serve between and care of active patients in isolated ward of hospitals and any kind of viral diseases. To keep minimum contact between active patients and medical authorities, we have devised the fabrication of automated trolley to deliver essentials (i.e. medicine, food & water bottles) to active patients without medical authorities meeting them. All the existing systems only deliver food and medicines and as such there is no provision of temperature sensors with trolley to record body temperature of patients, no self-sanitizing capabilities and UVC cabin. So, we are developing a small Arduino circuit to solve such problems. By successful implementation of such a project there will be medical authorities able to serve their duties without fear of being infected. It will be minimum possible contact between medical authorities and patients. The integrated temperature sensor to record daily body temperature of patients, automatic sanitization to sanitizes the path of trolley and UVC cabin to sanitize small goods. Our trolley capable of carrying approximately 10 to 15 kg and is functional in real time.

Keywords: Arduino, Automated trolley.

1. INTRODUCTION

- Ideal definition of an “automated trolley” is as follows:
- It needs to be capable of a reasonable-sized payload, at least a kilogram or more.
- It should be able to be “trained” to perform specific tasks.
- It needs to be able to handle obstacles that would prevent it from performing its tasks.
- It should be “aware” of its environment and be able to navigate within it with minimal human supervision.

Here we have divided this robot design into three main sections or “layers”:

- Navigation Layer
- Intelligence Layer
- Environment Input/output Layer

Figure 1 Automated Trolley Layout

Navigation Layer

The Navigation Layer performs movement and navigation of the robot. Robot here can operate independently or in conjunction with the other layers. One will be able to control the navigation layer using “high-level” or “low-level” commands. High-level commands include commands like “move forward to a position 3 meters ahead”, “move to co-ordinates x & y” or execute a preprogrammed movement. The robot will be able to handle situations when the position it is moving to is blocked by an obstacle. Low-level commands are more basic, things like “rotate the left wheel 4 turns and a specific speed”

Intelligence Layer

This is the “brains” of the robot. It controls the Navigation layer, and it communicates with the Environment Input/output layer. It also controls the robots master communications, allowing the device to interact with people. The main component of this layer will be a single-board computer (SBC) with a solid-state drive (SSD). We are currently choosing an SBC for this layer and currently the main contender is the HiKey970. This board is a powerful processor with a dedicated neural processor unit (NPU) and artificial intelligence capabilities. This layer will communicate with the other layers using Ethernet and

can also make use of Bluetooth and Wi-Fi. It will also have direct connections to some of the I/O devices such as video cameras.

Environment Input/output Layer

The final layer is the Environment I/O Layer. This layer allows the robot to interact with the outside world and explore its local environment. This layer is where all the non-navigation sensors are managed; by “non-navigation. Sensors in this layer include, but are not limited to:

- LiDAR to map the local environment.
- Speaker/Buzzer to make sound and voice.
- Temperature, Humidity and Light sensors.
- Proximity detectors

Problem Statement

In order to keep contact between active patients and medical authority’s minimum we have devised the fabrication of automated trolley to deliver food & medicine to active patients without medical authorities meeting them. Another problem faced by the medical staff is regular monitoring of temperature of patients while maintaining distance.

Objectives

1. To design automated trolley of suitable material and do structural analysis of it (Total deformation and stress induced at base part).
2. To record and monitor the body temperature of patients.
3. To validate the circuits by simulating them on online platform

Scope

1. To integrate temperature sensor along with trolley, this is first of its kind.
2. To make provision of automatic sanitizer dispenser for proper hygiene.
3. To disinfect the wearables like gloves, mask by provision of UV Cabin in trolley.

2. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 Methodology

Literature Review

Brem A., Viardot E. and Nylund P.A. focused their study on how technologies will help saving humanity if global pandemic like COVID-19 occurs again. Again, what are the technological challenges, related innovation logics and their social impact are considered. This pandemic has not only affected lives of people, but all the world economies are shaken by its effects.

Flexible Manufacturing Systems

During COVID crisis there has been number of cases where flexible manufacturing systems have helped the companies to change their production lines to produce some lifesaving equipment like ventilators for patients and hand sanitizers for medical staff.

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Yoganandhana A., Kannab G.R., Subhasha S.D., Jothi J.H. focused their study on retrospective and prospective use of robots in global pandemic and epidemic. They discovered how various robot shave been used in disease management mainly to limit the spread of this viral disease.

Medical Robots

There are various types of medical robots designed uniquely to perform a certain function or task. The design and structure of medical micro robots minimize the physical interactions with the cells of the immune system.

Cleaner Robots

Cleaners in healthcare systems are playing a major role in maintaining the regular cleanliness of hospitals and health care centers. During the situation like pandemic disease, the demand for such workers has increased many times, due to disease threat. Even, cleaning labor supplying companies are facing shortage of labor during this pandemic disease situation due to self-quarantine or other illnesses.

Ultra-violet light Robots

The spread of corona virus is due to nasal or mouth droplets when an infected person sneezes or coughs and that are inhaled by healthy person. Other means is due to when an infected person coughs or sneezes on some surface and that is touched by healthy person.

Mobile Robots

Mobile robots are designed to navigate and transport high risk patients to isolation wards by avoiding contact between healthcare workers and patients. They have cameras and sensors to record patient’s temperature, blood pressure and pulse rate

3. SIMULATION WORK

Numerical Simulation (Selection of Motor)

Total weight carries by trolley = 20 kg Diameter of wheel = 80 mm = 0.080 m Radius (r) = (0.080/2) = 0.040 m Speed (N) = 200 rpm

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$$\text{Torque}(T) = \text{Force} \times \text{Radius}$$

$$\text{Force} = \text{Mass} \times \text{Acceleration}$$

$$= 20 \times 9.81 = 196.2N$$

$$r = 0.040m$$

$$\text{Total} = 196.2 \times 0.040$$

$$\text{Total} = 7.848Nm$$

$$\text{Torque per wheel} = \left(\frac{7.848}{2}\right) = 3.924Nm$$

$$\text{Power} = \left(2 \times \pi \times \frac{N}{60}\right) \times (\text{Torque per wheel})$$

$$= (2 \times \pi \times N/60) \times (3.924)$$

$$\text{Power} = 82.18\text{watt}$$

$$H_p = \left(\frac{82.18}{746}\right) = 0.11016H_p$$

$$\text{Power} = \text{Voltage} \times \text{Current } P = V \times I$$

$$82.18 = 12 \times I = 6.848\text{Amp}$$

Design Simulation

The basic need of design is to know the actual requirement and the place of delivery, i.e. where is the trolley going to deliver the essentials. The dimensions of the trolley play an important role for the convenience of the patient. Design of the whole assembly consists of:

- Material selection for the Trolley
- Dimension selection
- CAD models

Material Selection

The COVID-19 disease is highly contagious which put all contacts of the patients in danger, including the medical personnel. So, robots which are immune to infection and easy to be disinfected, are recommended to play a vital role in pandemic. These below factors are considered in selecting the best material for the application.

- Materials must have adequate strength and corrosion resistance to safely handle the essentials.
- Materials should have no effect of sanitation on them.
- The system and environment temperature in which it operates depend on the material.
- Other factor is cost.

We could also use thermoplastics due to its lightweight properties, among metals another viable option can be Aluminium which also has lightweight making it easy to

manoeuvre but the cost plays an important role in this application. So, the stainless steel is better option as and alloy.

Comparison of Material Properties

Table 1 Comparison of Material Properties

Material Properties	Mild Steel	Stainless steel	Brass	Aluminium
Temperature (°C)	260	649	204	204
Rated pressure(kg/cm ²)	35000	20000	3000	4000
SUT(MPa)	841	505	345	250
Cost(kg/rs)	0.2857	0.005	0.00289	0.00881
Corrosion resistance	Good	Excellent	Good	Good

4. CONCLUSION

From the above table selected material is stainless steel.

Dimension selection

- The dimension of trolley is selected according to requirement of the patient. the concept of the trolley is quite like that of the delivery robots used by DHL (Dalsey, Hillblom and Lynn) which is used to lift heavy boxes and transport to packing stations.
- The length of the cart is critical to decide as the minimum distance between patients is about 8 ft (96 inches) and the aisle is also long. So, we decided to go with 60*60cm (2*2 ft) square at the base of the cart
- The height of the cart is also important parameter to decide as it should be easy for patient to grab things with ease.

The standard height of a hospital bed is approximately 50cms, so according to that we got the height of cart as 100cms from top to bottom.

5. CAD MODEL CATIA V5

The 3-D models are prepared in the computer software for mechanical, aeronautical design of machine components. It helps in creating a virtual representation of the component, which helps the user to modify and view the changes appeared virtually.

The weight of the cart is divided into the three parts:

- Food
- Mechanical Parts
- Electrical Parts

Base part:

- The electrical part (like 12v battery, wires) will be in the hollow part as shown in the below figure
- The electrical part (like 12v battery, wires) will be in the hollow part as shown in the below figure.
- The two thin identical sheet like part is to be used mounting of motor. Figure 3 Base part.

Figure 3 Base Part.

Caster Wheels

Figure 4 Caster Wheel

Frame

- The Frame consist of two parts, first is the sanitation box on the left-hand side of frame and second is the two food compartment shelves.
- The second shelf has UV rays light bulb as can be seen in the cad model below represented in blue colour, it is basically to kill the Covid-19 virus.
- The top will for the automated temperature sensor which will sense the temperature of the patient if it is above the desired temperature the buzzer will get ON and doctor will get informed.

Whole3-D Assembly

Figure 5 3-D Assembly

Whole 2D Drawing

Figure 6 Drawing of Whole Assembly.

6. GRAPHICAL SIMULATION

Temperature measurement of patients by using TMP36

We are taking the data of temperature of patients from the covid hospital according to that we are changing photo resistor on the tinker cad simulation software so temperature sensor sense that temperature and displaying on the screen.

Figure 7 Plot of Patients Vs Body temperature

Explanation: -

- Normal body temperature of human body is 37 degrees Celsius.
- The body temperatures that are measured on first day are greater than 37 degrees so that patients are advised to undergo covid test.
- After giving them proper treatment their temperature got reduced to average 37 degrees Celsius.
- So, temperature sensor integrated with our automated trolley helps to measure the temperature of every patient on daily basis and nurse gets to know about daily health condition of patients.

7. PIEZO (BUZZER) TEST ON TINKER CAD SOFTWARE

Figure 8 Piezo (buzzer) test on tinker cad software

Response Time of Automatic Hand Sanitizer

We are taking this test on this software by making the circuit of automatic sanitizer.

Figure 9 Time of Response of Automatic Hand Sanitizer

Table 2 average of response of time

Sr.no	1	2	3	4	5	6
Time of response	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

The average of response of time is 0.5 sec.

Time of response is constant throughout the process.

Experimental Validation

Remote control trolley by using transmitter and receiver

Circuit Diagram

Figure 4 Motor Driver Circuit

Components

- Receiver and Transmitter
- Dc motor
- L293D motor driver
- 2 Battery (5v)
- 1N4007 diode (8)

L293D motor driver

The L293D is a popular 16-Pin Motor Driver IC. As the name suggests it is mainly used to drive motors. A single L293D IC can run two DC motors at the same time; also, the direction of these two motors can be controlled independently. The L293D IC receives signals from the microprocessor and transmits the relative signal to the motors.

It has two voltage pins, one of which is used to draw current for the working of the L293D and the other is used to apply voltage to the motors.

DC Motor

A DC motor is any of a class of rotary electrical motors that converts direct current electrical energy into mechanical energy. The most common types rely on the forces produced by magnetic fields. Nearly all types of DC motors have some internal mechanism, either electromechanical or electronic; to periodically change the direction of current in part of the motor.

Transmitter and Receiver

In electronics and telecommunications, a transmitter or radio transmitter is an electronic device which produces radio waves with an antenna.

The transmitter itself generates a radio frequency alternating current, which is applied to the antenna. When excited by this alternating current, the antenna radiates radio waves.

Figure 5 block diagram of transmitter and receiver

A transmitter and a receiver combined in one unit are called a transceiver. The transmitter combines the information signal to be carried with the radio frequency signal which generates the radio waves, which is called the carrier signal. This process is called modulation.

Table 3 L293D Motor Driver Configuration Results

Receiver Input	L293D pin connection	Rotation of motor (1,2)	Direction of motion of trolley
D01	Pin-15 Pin-2	Clockwise	Forward Direction
D1	Pin-10 Pin-7	Anticlockwise	Reverse Direction
D2	Pin-15 Pin-7	Clockwise Anticlockwise	Left Direction
D3	Pin-10 Pin-2	Anticlockwise Clockwise	Right Direction

Construction and Working

- In L293D motor driver, pin 2 and pin 7 is connected to motor A and pin 10 and pin 15 is connected to motor B.
- When pin 2 and pin 15 is active then motor rotates in clockwise direction and when pin 10 and pin 7 is active then motor rotates in anticlockwise direction.
- When we press button 1 of transmitter D01 get on in the receiver. Pin 2 and 15 get on of motor driver so that each motor rotates in clockwise direction hence trolley move in forward direction.
- When we press button 2 of transmitter D1 get on in the receiver. Pin 10 and 7 get on of motor driver so that motor rotates in anticlockwise direction hence trolley move in backward direction.
- When we press button 3 of transmitter D2 get on in the receiver. Pin 15 and 7 get on of the motor driver so that motor A rotates in clockwise direction and motor B rotates in anticlockwise direction hence trolley turn in left direction.
- When we press button 4 of transmitter D3 get on the receiver. Pin 10 and 2 get on of the motor driver so that motor A rotates in anticlockwise direction and motor B rotates in clockwise direction hence trolley turn in right direction.

Figure 12 Motor Driver Simulation in Tinker cad

Automatic Alcohol Hand Sanitizer

Figure 13 Circuit diagram of Automatic Hand Sanitizer

Components

- Proximity Sensor
- Transistor Tip32
- Battery (9v)
- Mini dc pump 3v-9v
- Resistance 1KΩ

Proximity Sensor

- A proximity sensor is a sensor able to detect the presence of nearby objects without any physical contact.
- A proximity sensor often emits an electromagnetic field or a beam of electromagnetic radiation (infrared, for instance), and looks for changes in the field or return signal.
- Proximity sensors can have a high reliability and long functional life because of the absence of mechanical parts and lack of physical contact between the sensor and the sensed object. A proximity sensor adjusted to a very short range is often used as a touch switch. Detection distance: 2 ~ 30cm Detection angle: 35 ° Comparator chip: LM3933mm screw holes for easy mounting

Transistor tip 32C

A transistor is a semiconductor device used to amplify or switch electronic signals and electrical power. Transistors are one of the basic building blocks of modern electronics. It is composed of semiconductor material usually with at least three terminals for connection to an external circuit.

MINI Aquarium water Pump R385:

- Working voltage: DC 6-12V.
- Working current: 0.5-0.7A.
- Recommended voltage ratings are 9v 1A or 12v 1A.

- Maximum suck range of 2m.
- The maximum head range of 3m.
- Works with liquids of up to 80°C.
- The maximum flow rate of up to 1 – 3L/min.

Construction and Working

Figure 14 Construction and Working

When the patients put its hand close to proximity sensor it gets on and automatically sanitizer goes on patient hand without any touch with trolley. Patients meet proximity sensor then current get pass from the circuit and motor push the fluid in upward direction.

Potentiometer

A potentiometer is a three-terminal resistor with a sliding or rotating contact that forms an adjustable voltage divider

Temperature sensor

- The TMP36 is a low voltage, precision centigrade temperature sensor.
- It provides a voltage output that is linearly proportional to the Celsius temperature.
- It also doesn't require any external calibration to provide typical accuracies of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at $+25^\circ\text{C}$ and $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ over the -40°C to $+125^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range.

Piezo buzzer

A piezo buzzer is a type of electronic device that's used to produce a tone, alarm or sound.

It's lightweight with a simple construction, and it's typically a low-cost product.

Arduino Uno R3

Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P (datasheet).

It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator (CSTCE16M0V53 -R0), a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button.

It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started.

Figure 15 Experimental Validation on Tinker cad Software of Temperature Measurement Circuit

Figure 16 Experimental Validation of Proximity Sensor Circuit on Proteus8

Structural Analysis of Base plate

Steel

Figure 17 Equivalent (Von-Mises) Stress

Figure 18 Total Deformation

Figure 19 Normal Stress X-direction (top side)

Figure 20 Normal Stress Y-direction (top side)

Table 4 Results for Structural Analysis of Plate

Table 5 Parameters with Maximum Value

Sr.No.	Parameters	Maximum Value
1	Equivalent Stress	0.16615 MPa
2	Total deformation	8.2107×10-5mm
3	Normal Stress(x-direction)	0.016615 MPa
4	Normal Stress(y-direction)	0.016615 MPa

8. COST ANALYSIS

Table 6 Material & Machining Cost

Part	Material	P SQ P FT	MM	Total Product req in F	Total Cost
Base	Steel	240.0	360000.0	3.9	928.8
R+R Side	Steel	240.0	740000.0	8.0	1911.7
B Side	Steel	240.0	307840.0	3.3	795.3
P1	Steel	240.0	200000.0	2.2	516.7
P2	Steel	240.0	200000.0	2.2	516.7
Box 4 Slid	Steel	240.0	40000.0	0.4	103.3
Cutting		15.0	1847840.0	19.9	298.3
Transport					500.0
Total Cost					5570.7

Table 7 Cost of Standard Parts

Sr. No	DESCRIPTION	QTY	RATE/UNIT	TOTAL COST
1	Receiver & Transmitter	1	68	68
2	Dc motor	2	125	250
3	L293 motor driver	1	129	129
4	5-volt battery	2	229	458
5	9-volt battery	1	349	349
6	12-volt battery	1	1200	1200
7	Mini dc pump3v -9v	1	175	175
8	Resistor	2	3	6
9	Arduino Uno R3	1	585	585
10	Wheel 1. Wheel Castor wheel 2. Standard Wheel	2 2	180 150	360 300
11	Piezo (buzzer)	1	50	50
12	LCD (16*2)	1	380	380
13	LED	1	100	100
14	Potentiometer	1	109	109
15	IN4007 Diode	8	28	224
16	Sensor Temperature sensor Proximity sensor	1 1	85 200	85 200
17	Transistor tip 32	1	21	21
18	Wires		100	100
19	UV light bulb	1	275	275
20	Total			5464

Total Cost of Project

$$= \text{Cost of standard part} + \text{Cost of material and machining}$$

$$\text{Total Cost of Project} = 5464 + 5570.7 = 11034.7$$

9. CONCLUSION

- In practice, digitalization and automation did not progress fast before 2020 due to multiple reasons. The costs of robots are high, and the implementation is hesitating against the cheap labor.
- Until late 2020, the pandemic was still not well controlled globally. Many automation devices and systems have been deployed worldwide to fight against the crisis.

- Robot is one of the promising devices as it provides physical functionalities with effective social distancing among the patients and the medical staff.
- However, it needs to be noted that a fully automated robot is not available in all scenarios. Many of the robotic solutions so far still demand human supervision, while some of the autonomous ones are limited to simplified functionalities.

Future Scope

- Regarding future research trends, the technologies underneath is suggested to enhance robotics research:
- Real-time supply of medicinal goods and PPEs through Drones.
- Artificial Intelligence-based drug design and discovery.
- Mobile robots could be employed in the disposal of deceased bodies to prevent human contact and spread of the viral pathogens.
- Social robots are used in traffic management to reduce of mass gathering of people.
- Automated guided robots and mobile robots might be helpful to navigate, and transport stranded infected patients to healthcare centers or hospitals.
- Mobile robots will be helpful in the collection of samples for testing

REFERENCES

- [1] Thant ML, Mon KM, Tun KT. *Automatic hand - dryer*. International Journal of Creative and Innovative Research in All Studies 2019: PP 107-110.
- [2] Hanwate A, Thakare P., "Smart Trolley using RFID," International Journal of Research in Science and Engineering, pp. 2394-8299, 2015
- [3] Carlos erlan olival lima shigenori sano., "Design and analysis of a new type of mecanum wheel," International Journal of Research in Science and Engineering, 2015
- [4] Akshay Sharma, "Automatic Sanitizer Dispensing Machine,". International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) <http://www.ijert.org> ISSN: 2278- 0181 IJERTV9IS070307 Vol. 9 Issue 07, July-2020
- [5] L. Subhashree, D. Sruthiraj, S. Vinitha, Joeljosephson, "A survey of trolley/wheelchair based smart system for exclusive medical applications", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology Volume: 05 Issue: 03 | Mar-2018 2395-0072
- [6] Ng YL, et al., "Automatic Humang Shopping Trolley with Smart Shopping System," Journal Technology, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 49-56, 2015.
- [7] Seema U., et al., "Smart Trolley Follower using Vision based Technique," IJCA Proceedings on

National Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Networking ACCNET 2016, vol.7, pp. 8-10, 2016.

- [8] Ferdoush S and Li X., "Wireless Sensor Network System Design Using Raspberry Pi and Arduino for Environmental Monitoring Applications," Procedia Computer Science, vol. 34, pp. 103-110, Jan 2014. 16.12.2021 6:48 pm.